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Genes that mediate progression to carcinoma following high-risk HPV infection.

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We conducted an expression screen to discover genes important for transformation *in vivo* by measuring total transcription in the human cervix during the course of cancer progression from the normal cervix to cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) and frank tumor following infection with high-risk human papillomavirus.